

DEVELOPMENT OF REMEDIAL ACTIONS FOR REHABILITATING BLACK SEA COASTAL AREAS AFFECTED BY MINING ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

Important mining and ore processing centers at the Bulgarian and Romanian Black Sea coast, such as Vromos Bay, in Bulgaria, Navodari and Baia close to Constanta, and Somova close to the Danube Delta in Romania, have produced millions of tons of wastes that are characterized as radioactive, toxic and hazardous. Soils, groundwaters and the Black Sea in these areas are severely contaminated either by the dissolution of heavy elements and radionuclides contained in the tailings or by the uncontrolled discharge of effluents and decant waters. In the present paper, all above mentioned sources of pollution that are currently directly or indirectly affecting humans, soils, freshwater ecosystems and the Black Sea, are identified and characterized. Furthermore, in order to assess the level of risk posed by each source of pollution, a complete environmental characterization study was undertaken followed by a risk analysis based on a source-pathway-target basis. Based on experimental and risk analysis data, several viable preventative and remedial technologies were studied in detail in the laboratory. Finally, an in situ rehabilitation scheme is currently underway at Vromos Bay and Navodari, aiming at deactivating the pollution sources and rehabilitating the contaminated areas. This scheme involves clean up of waters loaded with toxic elements with the application of a passive treatment system and development of a vegetative cover on phosphogypsum and sulphidic tailings.

1. INTRODUCTION

Intensive mining and ore processing activities over the last fifty years, in coastal areas in Bulgaria and Romania, have resulted in the production of millions of tons of mining wastes and tailings that are characterized as radioactive, toxic and hazardous.

At Vromos Bay, south of Burgas in Bulgaria, 8 million tons of copper tailings from Rossen flotation plant have been disposed between 1954 and 1977 on the beach. Since then, tailings are discharged in a constructed tailings dam. Dissolution of heavy elements and radionuclides contained in the tailings endangers the entire ecosystem in this area.

At Navodari, north of Constanta in Romania, more than 3 million cubic meters of phosphogypsum tailings and 1 million cubic meters of pyritic cinders have been disposed in several dumps causing contamination of soils and groundwaters by the solubilisation of heavy elements and radionuclides. In addition, the discharge of decant waters from the operating phosphogypsum decantation pond to the Black Sea, often without any pretreatment, causes severe environmental pollution.

At Baia, north of Navodari, over 1.2 million tons of copper tailings from the nearby located flotation plant have been disposed since 1965 in three dumps. These tailings exhibit a considerable potential for acidic water generation, high TCLP toxicity and elevated bioavailable fractions of copper, zinc and iron. In addition, due to the lack of a vegetative cover, aerial transfer of fine particles and solubilisation of heavy elements causes contamination of surrounding soils and waters.

At Somova, close to Tulcea in Romania, at the start of the extended Danube delta, mining and processing activities of baryte and complex sulphidic ores have resulted in the disposal of over 2.5 million tons of tailings, endangering an area, which is characterized as a protected biosphere.

In this paper, the main sources of pollution that are currently directly or indirectly affecting humans, soils, freshwater ecosystems and the Black Sea are identified and characterized. In order to assess the risk that these tailings pose to the environment a detailed sampling campaign was carried out (Kontopoulos et al., 1996a, 1996b) involving collection of surface and drill core samples and determination of the main geotechnical parameters of the tailings. Drill core samples were subjected to chemical and mineralogical analyses, determination of their acid generation potential with the

application of static tests (acid-base accounting) and determination of their toxicity with the application of the EPA TCLP test. Several samples were subjected to leaching with EDTA to determine the bioavailable fraction of toxic metals; a limited number of samples were subjected to the sequential extraction procedure to determine the speciation of heavy metals. The bioavailable fraction of the toxic elements was checked against the Netherlands, the Canadian and the national guidelines for soils and the toxicity of the tailings was compared against the toxicity limits set by the TCLP test. Surface and pore water quality was monitored regularly and checked against existing national effluent standards. Radioactivity measurements were also conducted and concentration of radionuclides in tailings, decant waters, surface streams and soils was compared against national standards. Furthermore, in order to assess the level of risk posed by each source of pollution at each affected area, a risk analysis based on a source-pathway-target basis was undertaken. Based on experimental and risk analysis data several viable preventative and remedial technologies were examined in detail in the laboratory. This study involved solubilisation of pollutants from the tailings, application of wet, dry and organic covers for the prevention of acidic water generation and clean up of the effluents loaded with toxic elements by applying a passive treatment system or by the use of biosorbents. After a critical evaluation of all examined technologies, an in situ application of the most viable technologies has been decided. This latter scheme involves mainly: clean up of effluents and leachates at Vromos Bay in Bulgaria, by the application of a passive treatment system operating under continuous flow conditions and development of a vegetative cover on phosphogypsum tailings at Navodari in Romania. The establishment of such cover involves study of the potential and growth characteristics for various perennial herbaceous species and bushes after the addition of several amendments such as dolomite, kaolin, bentonite, sewage sludge and soil in several configurations in order to increase soil pH and add nutrients in the system.

2. METHODOLOGY - EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Environmental characterization of pollution sources

The methodology that was applied for the environmental characterization of all pollution sources is briefly presented in the following table (Kontopoulos et al., 1995).

Table 1: Methodology for environmental characterization of pollution sources

<i>Sampling</i>	<i>Chemical Analyses</i>	<i>Mineralogical Analyses</i>	<i>Geotechnical characteristics</i>	<i>Toxicity characteristics</i>	<i>Radioactivity</i>
1. Surface samples	1. Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry	1. XRD combined with optical microscopy	1. Particle size distribution	1. NNP 2. TCLP	1. Gamma radiation
2. Low depth samples	2. LECO Sulfur Analyzer	2. SEM techniques	2. Permeability 3. Wet bulk / true density	3. Phytoavailable fraction (EDTA) 4. Sequential extraction	2. Specific activity of Ra-226 3. α -activity

2.2. Experimental procedure

The experimental procedure followed for the study of techniques in order to decontaminate tailings, effluents and prevent further environmental pollution is as follows:

2.2.1. Tailings decontamination

In order to study the mechanisms of solubilisation of different pollutants from the flotation tailings and soils at Vromos Bay leaching tests were conducted in lysimeters, mechanically stirred reactors and shake flasks. In lysimeters, leaching solution was percolated through the flotation tailings dissolving different components. Tests conducted in mechanically stirred reactors involved chemical leaching of flotation tailings at 20% w/v pulp density and 20° C for 48h with the use of the following reagents: H₂SO₄, Fe₂(SO₄)₃, HCl, FeCl₃, KHSO₅ (oxone), oxalic acid, KCl, Na₂CO₃ and NaHCO₃. Tests conducted in shake flasks involved biological leaching of flotation tailings at 20% w/v pulp density and 20° C for 14 days with the use of nutrients and several mixed enrichment cultures. Similar tests, in bioreactors and Erlenmeyer flasks were conducted in order to study the leaching behavior of the toxic elements contained in the sulphidic tailings of Baia, Romania. Parameters studied were: pH, Eh, temperature, dissolved oxygen, total dissolved solids, total suspended solids, alkalinity and concentration of heavy metals and radionuclides in solution.

2.2.2. Effluents clean up

In order to study the removal of toxic and radioactive elements from the effluents emanating from tailings at Vromos bay, a laboratory passive treatment system operating under continuous flow conditions and consisting of an anaerobic cell, an aerobic cell and a filter system was used. The

anaerobic cell was filled with organic matter consisting of spent mushroom compost, cow manure and saw dust. A stable microbial community consisting of different microorganisms was then established in the cell within one month of cultivation. The aerobic cell was filled with crushed ceramics, which act as an inert matrix to support the development of microbial films consisting of different microorganisms, mainly aerobic heterotrophic bacteria. Artificial aeration was applied periodically to enhance growth and activity of the aerobic microbial community. The filter system comprises a sand filter with a volume of 2 l and an activated carbon filter with a volume of 0.3 l. Both filters were connected in series. For the clean up of acidic leachates in Romania, biosorption was considered as a viable technique. Biosorption tests were conducted in glass columns filled with several biosorbents as substrates such as activated charcoal, molecular sieve, shell sand, chiselgur, penicillium biomass and aspergillus niger biomass.

2.2.3. Application of covers for pollution prevention

The study of the application of covers for the prevention of pollution emanating from the dissolution of toxic elements from the tailing dumps involves study of wet, dry, organic and vegetative covers.

The study of wet, dry and organic covers, involves tests conducted in laboratory columns where tailings were placed in the lower part of the column covered either with a layer of water or several layers of materials such as limestone gravel, clay minerals, soils and municipal sewage sludge. The height of the layers for water as well as for all other materials used varied. Parameters studied involved quality of leachate, oxygen content at various heights within the column, pH, Eh and acidity/alkalinity.

The study of vegetative covers involves study of species that can grow on phosphogypsum dumps in Navodari and sulphidic tailing dumps in Baia. Glasshouse pot tests conducted using in several configurations a variety of herbaceous species and bushes, which show a potential and tolerance for growth in such environments. Amendments such as dolomite, kaolin, bentonite, sewage sludge and clean soil were added in several configurations in order to increase soil pH and to add nutrients in the substrate.

2.3. Risk assessment study

A risk assessment study was performed in order to assess the environmental risks associated with mining wastes and effluents at all case study sites in Bulgaria and Romania (Copernicus Mid-term assessment report, 1998). Hazards or potential sources of contamination that may lead to some form of harm on the local environment were identified and evaluated. This was carried out by establishing whether a plausible source-pathway-target relationship exists, such that targets could be exposed to or affected by a hazard. For each plausible pollutant pathway identified, a risk assessment was undertaken. The risk was evaluated by assessing the probability of the hazard reaching the target as well as by assessing the significance of the impact should the hazard reach the target.

3. RESULTS - DISCUSSION

3.1. Environmental characterization of pollution sources

The environmental characterization of all pollution sources reveals for each case study area the following:

3.1.1. Vromos Bay (BG)

- The tailings at the tailings dam are quite fine (78% -0.125 mm) and contain low levels of residual sulfides (1-3%). Their permeability is considered high (2.5×10^{-4} cm/s). Their potential for generating acidity (60 kg CaCO_3/t) and their TCLP toxicity are considered low.
- Bioavailable fractions of Pb, Zn and Cu are considered substantial (115, 35, 154 mg/kg respectively). The specific activity of the radionuclides U-238 and Ra-226 is considered high (1255 and 2725 Bq/kg respectively).
- Soils in the area under study are characterized by elevated concentrations of heavy metals and radionuclides which often exceed Bulgarian standards set for agricultural use (2218 mg/kg Cu, 141 mg/kg Pb, 110 mg/kg Zn, 410 Bq/kg U-238, 1160 Bq/kg Th-232 and 410 Bq/kg Pb-214).
- The two existing streams in the area, discharging effluents from the tailings dam to the sea are characterized by neutral-alkaline pH values, low concentration of heavy metals and high concentration of anions (up to 15000 mg/l chlorides and up to 3280 mg/l sulfates) and radionuclides. The presence of higher concentrations of toxic metals and radionuclides locally in both streams is connected with the activity of several existing groups of heterotrophic bacteria.
- The quality of the water in the natural wetland located close to the bay, which receives part of the effluents from the streams, is substantially better (up to 12000 mg/l chlorides and up to 1700 mg/l

sulfates). This is due to the physicochemical reactions occurring in a wetland which assist in clean up of water.

- The risk assessment study has shown that the major risks for this area are: increased radiation levels for humans and livestock through the radioactive decay, surface drainage which deteriorates surface water quality and affects humans, crops and livestock as well as freshwater ecosystems and the Black Sea, wind erosion which causes deposition of fine particles containing heavy metals and radionuclides on crops and solubilisation of heavy metals and radionuclides which affects surface water quality and crops.

3.1.2. Navodari (RO)

- Phosphogypsum tailings are quite fine (32% - 0.08 mm). They are characterized by low-neutral paste pH values (4-6) and contain elevated concentrations of heavy elements and radionuclides (177300 mg/kg S(SO₄²⁻), 34.5 mg/kg Pb, 4.5 mg/kg Cd, 475 Bq/kg Ra-226 and 442 Bq/kg Pb-210). The main concern from the radioactivity associated to Ra-226 is the emanation of radon-222 gas.
- TCLP toxicity for phosphogypsum tailings is considered low. Bioavailable fractions of heavy elements are high (mg/kg): Fe:424, Zn:8.7, Cu:25.8
- Decant water from the operating pond, which is often discharged without any neutralization to the Black Sea, is characterized by acidic-neutral pH values (2.75-5.4), elevated concentrations of cadmium (up to 29 mg/l), fluorine (up to 207 mg/l), sulfates (up to 1720 mg/l), phosphates (up to 1270 mg/l) and Th-234 (up to 7.5 Bq/l).
- Cinders chemical analysis is (mg/kg): S:10000, Fe:480000, Al:4000, Pb:2540, Zn:1700, As:2000, Cu:1500.
- The risk assessment study has shown that the major risks for this area are: inhalation of dust by residents as well as deposition of dust on agricultural lands, solubilisation of heavy metals and anions from phosphogypsum stacks and pyritic cinders dump, contamination of groundwater abstraction for potable supply and finally contamination of the Black Sea. Dry ash analysis of plants grown on the dumps shows elevated concentration of heavy metals in plant tissue (mg/kg): Pb:500-5000, Zn:1400-3000, Cu:700-3000 and Ra-226:50-370 Bq/kg.

3.1.3. Baia (RO)

- Baia sulphidic tailings are characterized by elevated content of heavy metals and sulfur (mg/kg): Fe: 66100, Al: 5990, Cu: 715, Pb: 525, S(SO₄²⁻): 27400. They exhibit a considerable potential for acidic water generation (paste pH: 2.37, NNP: -91 kg CaCO₃/t of tailings).
- Their TCLP toxicity is considered in general low, but the bioavailable fractions of heavy metals are considered elevated in terms of iron, zinc and copper (mg/kg): Fe: 40.7, Zn: 21.4 and Cu: 15.
- Decant water contains elevated concentration of cadmium (5 mg/l).
- The risk assessment study has shown that the major risks for this area are: inhalation of dust by residents as well as deposition of dust on agricultural lands and surface drainage which deteriorates surface water quality and affects humans, crops and livestock.

3.1.4. Somova (RO)

- Tailings are in general characterized by low content of heavy metals and sulfides and elevated concentrations of neutralizing minerals (mg/kg): Al: 19700, Pb: 895, Zn: 1010, Ca: 18300 and Mg: 46900. The main mineralogical phases are: quartz, feldspar, dolomite, chlorite, illite.
- Their TCLP toxicity is considered in general low and the bioavailable fractions are considered elevated only for lead and zinc (mg/kg): Pb: 56, Zn: 40.5.
- The risk assessment study has shown that the major risks for this area are: deterioration of surface water quality in an area located at the start of the extended Danube Delta which is regarded as a protected ecosystem and contamination of surface water used for irrigation through increased atmospheric dust levels

From the above analysis, it is concluded that the areas of Vromos Bay, Navodari and Baia have been severely affected and therefore rehabilitation schemes are needed. Somova tailings seem to constitute a minor hazard for the ecosystem and no rehabilitation schemes are proposed.

3.2. Viable rehabilitation schemes

3.2.1. Tailings decontamination

Tests conducted in lysimeters, mechanically stirred reactors and shake flasks have shown that:

- heavy elements and radionuclides contained in tailings at Vromos Bay can be solubilised to a higher or lesser extent. Higher solubilisation of radioactive as well as heavy metals takes place in the presence of higher concentrations of soluble organic compounds.
- lysimeter tests show that uranium is the most efficiently leached pollutant: 3.43% of uranium was solubilised within 124 days. It must be noted that part of solubilised uranium is precipitated again in the form of insoluble compounds. Radium and thorium were also solubilised but at lower rates. Solubilisation of heavy metals (copper, zinc, lead) occurs at lower rates compared to solubilisation of radioactive elements (1%).
- chemical leaching, with the use of oxidation agents, improves dramatically solubilisation of radioactive elements (up to 60% for uranium and 40% for radium). This shows that most of uranium in the tailings is in the tetravalent state and therefore its solubilisation is connected with a prior oxidation to the hexavalent state.
- several microbial catalyzed processes can assist in solubilisation of radionuclides and toxic heavy metals from the tailings. It has been shown that different heterotrophic bacteria are able to solubilise uranium by at least two different mechanisms. The first mechanism is related to the microbial production of peroxide compounds that oxidize tetravalent uranium to the hexavalent state. U^{6+} is then solubilised as uranyl carbonate or in the form of organic complexes. The second mechanism is related to the microbial secretion of some organic metabolites, mainly organic acids, which form complexes with this metal. Toxic heavy metals are solubilised from the relevant easily leachable fractions of the tailings mainly by means of microbial secreted organic acids. Iron and manganese are, however, solubilised as a result of an enzymatic reduction of Fe^{3+} and Mn^{4+} to the relevant bivalent forms. This is due to the activity of some chemolithotrophic bacteria, mainly related to the species *Thiobacillus thioparus* and *Thiobacillus neapolitanus*. These bacteria enhance oxidation of sulfide minerals by removing the passivation film of S^0 deposited on the mineral surface, by different chemical, electrochemical and biological processes.
- Biosolubilisation tests conducted in fermentors with sulphidic tailings from Baia have shown that high extraction percentages of heavy elements can be attained: 50% for Cu, 46.4% for Zn, 24% for Pb, 31.4% for Fe and 50% for As.

3.2.2. Leachates clean up

Biosorption tests have shown that several biosorbents can achieve sufficient removal of heavy elements from leachates emanating from copper dumps in Romania. Maximum removal percentages attained with the use of activated charcoal, fungal biomass and diatomite were: 28.5% for Cu, 19.2% for Zn, 61.5% for Pb, 60% for Fe and 10% for Al.

3.2.3. Application of wet, dry and organic covers for pollution prevention

Preliminary data from the application of wet, dry and organic covers for the prevention of pollution emanating from sulphidic tailing dumps have shown that these schemes can be considered as viable preventative options. The main functions of these covers, depending on their composition are: to act as physical and chemical barriers preventing oxygen diffusion into the tailings mass; to temporarily store rain water and return it later to the atmosphere via evapotranspiration; to isolate tailings from the environment and eliminate wind erosion and dusting; to inhibit acidic water production; and finally assist in sulphate reduction and sulphate and hydroxide precipitation reactions (Kontopoulos et al., 1996a; 1996b, Wildeman et al., 1993, Pierce et al., 1994, Tasse et al., 1997). The quality of the effluents has been improved in terms of pH, Eh, concentration of heavy elements and total dissolved solids, but the effectiveness of these options will be critically assessed after a simulation period of two hydrological years.

3.2.4. Clean up of effluents at Vromos Bay with the use of a passive treatment system

The application of a passive treatment system for the clean up of effluents at Vromos Bay shows that:

- Efficient removal of radioactive elements, toxic heavy metals and sulfate ions is achieved in the anaerobic cell. Heavy metals are mainly precipitated as sulfides with the action of hydrogen sulfide produced as a result of the bacterial dissimilatory sulfate reduction. A significant part of uranium is precipitated as a result of reduction of hexavalent uranium to the tetravalent state.
- Remaining uranium as well as other radioactive elements present in effluents, i.e. radium and thorium, are removed mainly by sorption on the organic matter. Chloride ions are also removed by sorption on the organic matter.
- Treatment of effluents in the anaerobic cell is related with an increase of the soluble organic substances to levels much higher than the permissible levels for waters used in agriculture and/or in industry. The soluble organic substances were obtained as a result of the activity of different

saprophytic microorganisms (mainly cellulose-degrading microorganisms) which degraded the biopolymeric organic compounds and provided the sulfate-reducing bacteria with suitable monomers organic sources of carbon and energy (mainly organic acids). In the course of time the amount of the organic substances solubilised as a result of the microbial activity was markedly decreased. The concentration of NH_4^+ ions in effluents was considerably increased due to the ammonification processes during biodegradation of the organic matter. The concentration of phosphate ions was also increased and this is connected with the solubilisation of some phosphates present in the spent mushroom compost. Regardless of the presence of iron chips in the anaerobic cell, effluents still contained high concentrations of hydrogen sulfide.

- In the aerobic cell, the intensive growth and activity of the heterotrophic microorganisms resulted in a significant decrease in the concentration of soluble organic compounds in water. However, all essential parameters connected with the presence of such compounds (i.e. permanganate, dissolved organic carbon, chemical oxygen demand and biological oxygen demand) were still much higher than the relevant permissible levels for waters intended for industrial use.
- Hydrogen sulfide was completely removed through its oxidation by chemolithotrophic bacteria (mainly related to the species *Thiobacillus thioautotrophicus*) present in the aerobic cell. NH_4^+ ions were also removed through their oxidation to nitrates by chemolithotrophic nitrifying bacteria.
- The concentration of chloride ions was further decreased due to both precipitation and sorption processes.

3.2.5 Application of a vegetative cover on sulphidic and phosphogypsum tailings in Romania

The application of glasshouse pot tests in laboratory and larger scale indicates that:

- Paste pH in all experiments, as increased by the addition of amendments, can support plant growth.
- Most amendments used for the addition of nutrients, provide sufficient amounts of extractable elements and nutrients to the substrate.
- Preliminary field tests have shown that a number of perennial plants and bushes which were planted on Navodari phosphogypsum tailings as well as on Baia sulphidic tailings show an excellent growth intensity and can be used for the establishment of a vegetative cover.

After a critical evaluation of the above mentioned techniques, the last two were selected for an in situ application on a larger scale at the case study sites in Bulgaria and Romania. First data recorded, after an application period of 6 months, show that both schemes exhibit high efficiency in decontaminating effluents at Vromos Bay and rehabilitating phosphogypsum tailing dumps with the establishment of a vegetative cover at Navodari. Final conclusions will be derived though after the spring of next year.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The main sources of pollution that are currently directly or indirectly affect the quality of the water in the Black Sea, at the areas of Vromos Bay, in Bulgaria, Navodari and Baia close to Constanta, and Somova close to the Danube Delta in Romania were identified and characterized; they were the flotation tailings disposed at the tailings dam, the beach tailings and the leachates in Vromos Bay, the phosphogypsum tailings, the pyritic cinders and the decant waters in Navodari, the sulphidic tailings in Baia and the baryte and complex sulphidic tailings in Somova.

Risk analysis based on the source-pathway-target principle showed that all pollution sources constitute, to a higher or lesser extent, a serious hazard for humans, soils and freshwater ecosystems in the area.

Based on the above findings, a rehabilitation strategy was developed for each affected area, aiming at deactivating the pollution sources and rehabilitating the contaminated areas with preventative and remedial actions.

A synopsis of this strategy is shown below:

For Vromos Bay it is believed that the application of solubilisation techniques for the removal of heavy metals and radionuclides from mining tailings and soils does not seem a viable rehabilitation technique, mainly due to the high cost involved. The key factors required for the successful implementation of leaching processes are: efficient removal of the metals to meet regulatory criteria for the treated soils, minimization of liquid effluents and compliance with environmental discharge regulations, and an affordable cost. On the contrary, adequate clean up of effluents can be achieved in a passive treatment system. This system seems to offer a low cost and maintenance free solution for the treatment and purification of the leachates entering Vromos bay, as seen from the experimental data and the improved quality of the waters in the natural wetland already existing on site. A semi-pilot

scale passive treatment system operating under continuous flow conditions is has already been under operation on site.

For Navodari and Baia, the application of solubilisation and biosorption techniques for the removal of heavy metals and radionuclides from mining tailings and effluents also does not seem as a viable rehabilitation scheme, due to the high cost required for an in-situ application. On the other hand the application of a vegetative cover, as shown from the field semi-pilot scale application, with the use of herbaceous species and bushes which show a potential and tolerance for growth in such environments, offers a much better prospective and it is believed that it will reduce erosion and aerial transfer of fine particles, improve surface runoff quality, promote dump use as a habitat and improve aesthetics in the affected areas. Finally, the application of wet, dry and organic covers for rehabilitating tailing dumps seems to be an interesting alternative, but more time is needed for a critical evaluation of such schemes.

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